

INNO4CFIs

Regenerative Carbon Farming

Deliverable 9.1 Quality Assurance Plan

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Table of Contents

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	6
1. Introduction	6
1.1 Work package structure, deliverables and indicators of progress	7
1.2 The consortium structure	12
1.3 Impact of the project	14
2. Project management approach	18
2.1 Overall Management strategy	18
2.2 Project management structure	19
2.3 Management Procedures	20
3. Quality Expectations	22
3.1 Quality of the project implementation	22
3.2 Quality of project deliverables	22
3.2.1 Quality of document based deliverables	23
3.2.2 Quality of INNO4CFIs events	23
3.2.3 Quality of promotion materials	25
3.2.4 Quality of websites and other electronic tools	25
3.2.5 Quality of project management	25
4. Internal monitoring	26
4.1 Project quality assurance strategy	26
4.2 Quality responsibilities	26
4.2.1 Task Leader (responsible for the deliverable)	26
4.2.2 Reviewers (other partners involved in the activity, co-authors)	27
4.2.3 WP Leader	27
4.2.4 Quality Assurance Project Team	28
4.2.5 Project Coordinator	28
4.2.6 Steering Committee	28
4.3 Quality feedback by the target groups	28
4.4 Risk Management	29
4.4.1 Practical approach to risk identification	29
4.4.2 Risk/Uncertainties monitoring procedure	30
4.4.3 Risk Response development	30
5. External Monitoring	35
6. Effort and Cost management	36

6.1	Effort and cost management approach	36
6.2	Guidelines for Unplanned Expenses	36
6.3	Measuring project effort and costs	37
6.4	Subcontracting	37
7.	Schedule management plan	40
7.1	Schedule control	44
8.	Evaluation system	45
8.1	Consortium Assessment	46
8.2	KPIs and Impact Assessment	47
8.3	Stakeholder assessment	49
8.4	Cascade funding assessment	50
ANNEXES		52
	ANNEX I – Deliverable Template	53
	ANNEX II – INNO4CFIs Master	63
	ANNEX III – Deliverable Quality Assurance Check	65
	ANNEX IV – Participant Feedback Form	67
	ANNEX V – Event Report Template	70
	ANNEX VI – Risk Monitoring Sheet	74

Executive Summary

The “Quality Assurance Plan” is a deliverable within WP9 entitled “Quality” of the INNO4CFIs project (Nature-Based Business Model and Emerging Innovations to enhance Carbon Farming Initiatives (CFIs) while preserving Biodiversity, Water Security and Soil Health).

The plan outlines the main definitions related to quality management. It then defines processes for planning and executing the project activities in order to ensure the highest possible quality. The manual sets the minimum principles, requirements and processes needed to implement an effective quality assurance and control.

In order to continuously evaluate the project with regard to the attainment of its objectives and quality, a coherent evaluation system is developed and introduced by this document taking into account the multidimensional aspects of the project itself. The evaluation system aims to assess the progress and success of the project as well as to identify potential improvement sources.

In conclusion, all the data that are part of the present deliverable refer to the existing G.A., and they will be consequently updated in case the amendment submitted in M3 will be approved by the Granting Authority.

1. Introduction

Quality management is the process of defining the strategy and methods the project will deploy to ensure the project’s deliverables are of acceptable quality before they are delivered. Quality management addresses all the issues related to quality assurance, self-assessment and any ethical issues. For these reasons, INNO4CFIs has foreseen an entire WP, i.e. WP9 Quality Assurance, fully dedicated to it.

Quality management is fundamental to the success of the project, and the project adopts a methodology with two separated processes:

- Quality assurance which is the execution of processes and procedures to ensure the achievement of quality, to assure that the project satisfies the needs for which it was undertaken;
- Quality control which verifies and assesses the achievement/product; it is concerned with the operational activities and techniques that are used to fulfil the requirements of quality. Quality control is an integral part of the project and aims to ensure that objectives are met in the most effective way. This QAP defines the general approach to quality control, cross-package appraisal, internal and external evaluation and the strategy for how the quality control mechanisms will be applied so that the operational, management and working procedures are comprehensively monitored and improved throughout the project duration.
- Quality management is the responsibility of the PC which ensures quality of the project management and consequently, of all deliverables and provides measurement criteria to verify the success of the project.

The Work Plan of the INNO4CFIs project describes milestones and the acceptance criteria for each phase of the project. Assessing adherence to these baseline conditions provides the method for evaluating both the project and its services.

Quality organisation is under the responsibility of the Project Coordinator (PC). The PC is supported by the Project Manager (PM) in the definition and in the execution of the control activities planned or considered useful during the INNO4CFIs project. The Project Coordinator receives also support, advice and help at several levels:

- from Work Package leaders in several quality functions related to the delivery process. Activities leaders are fully responsible for scientific and technical quality check of all deliverables.
- from the European Commission. The European Commission, through the Project Adviser, may provide advice on any quality issue related to the project. The Work Package Leaders may also request advice from the Project Officer on quality issues whenever necessary, usually communicating through the Project Coordinator.

The Project Coordinator is in charge of ensuring that deliverables to be submitted are structured, harmonised and organised to ensure that they are timely, exhaustive, clear and effective.

All the specific procedures related to Quality Assurance are set out in the Quality Assurance Plan of INNO4CFIs.

The Quality Assurance Plan (QAP) formalises the approach that will be followed by the partners of the INNO4CFIs project to ensure the highest possible quality of the project activities, outputs and outcomes and project management.

This document defines the procedures for:

- Internal monitoring, quality and risk management
- External monitoring
- Partners' technical and financial reporting

The document also defines the quality expectations regarding the project deliverables, i.e. reports and documents, events/workshops/meetings as well as the procedures for internal and external monitoring.

The QAP contains a set of scheduled activities and defines the objectives, roles and responsibilities. The QAP includes established indicators, methodology and procedures for evaluation of project activities and results. For each task it determines the responsible partner(s), timeframe and tools of implementation, the expected results or products, as well as the respective quality criteria.

The QAP elaborated in the frame of WP9 is strictly linked to the activities of Project Coordination as part of WP1 as well as to the Project Management Strategy presented at kick-off meeting and shared by the PC in M2 as part of Milestone 1 output.

1.1 Work package structure, deliverables and indicators of progress

All INNO4CFIs activities are divided into 10 work packages, to allow project managers a finer level of control over assignments, as well as allow simultaneous work to be done on different components of the project. Once the teams have finished their individual work packages, the entire project comes together with seamless integration. Completion of a work package is most often overseen by a specific person: a manager, supervisor, a team lead, or a designated team member.

WPs and deliverables of INNO4CFIs are given in table 1:

#	Title of expected deliverable	Type of expected deliverable	Due Date
<u>WP1: Project Management</u>			
D.1.1	Data Management Plan – 1 st release	DMP — Data Management Plan	M3
D1.2	Data Management Plan – 2 nd release	DMP — Data Management Plan	M18
D1.3	Progress report	R — Document, report	M18
D1.4	Data Management Plan – Final release	DMP — Data Management Plan	M18
D.1.1	Data Management Plan – 1 st release	DMP — Data Management Plan	M36
<u>WP2: WEF E Nexus and stakeholder analysis</u>			
D2.1	Inventory of the success cases and go-to-business scenario – 1 st release	R — Document, report	M6
D2.2	Report on Needs of low and moderate innovative regions – 1 st release	R — Document, report	M6
D2.3	Inventory of the success cases and go-to-business scenario – 2 nd release	R — Document, report	M18
D2.4	Report on Needs of low and moderate innovative regions – 2 nd release	R — Document, report	M18
D2.5	KPIs inventory	R — Document, report	M18
D2.6	INNO4CFIs: self-assessment tool for SMEs	R — Document, report	M24
D2.7	Inventory of the success cases and go-to-business scenario - final release	R — Document, report	M36
D2.8	Report on Needs of low and moderate innovative regions	R — Document, report	M36
<u>WP3: Technology Maturation</u>			

#	Title of expected deliverable	Type of expected deliverable	Due Date
D3.1	Tech Carbon Footprint Report and KPIs – 1 st release	R — Document, report	M12
D3.2	MTP Upgrade Report	R — Document, report	M12
D3.3	Tech Carbon Footprint Report and KPIs – Final release	R — Document, report	M18
D3.4	Life Cycle Assessment Report	R — Document, report	M18
<u>WP4: Artificial Intelligence and satellite observation</u>			
D4.1	Earth Observation Assessment Report – 1 st release	R — Document, report	M6
D4.2	Earth Observation Assessment Report - final release	R — Document, report	M24
D4.3	UAV data Report	R — Document, report	M24
D4.4	Carbon credit recommendation system based on ethical and social AI.	R — Document, report	M24
<u>WP5: Green Blockchain & Carbon Credits</u>			
D5.1	Digital identity techniques and connectors for interoperability with eIDAS	DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	M16
D5.2	Low-power DLT P2P CC smart contract execution environment	DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	M24
<u>WP6: Validation</u>			
D6.1	Agroforestry project design	DATA — data sets, microdata, etc	M6
D6.2	KPIs assessment report	DATA — data sets, microdata, etc	M24

#	Title of expected deliverable	Type of expected deliverable	Due Date
D6.3	Biodiversity Carbon Credit Report	R — Document, report	M30
D6.4	Stakeholders guidelines: design establishment and evaluation of the INNO4CFIs Carbon Credit Model	R — Document, report	M36
D6.5	End users questionnaires	R — Document, report	M18
<u>WP7: Mangrove Carbon Farming Business Model</u>			
D7.1	Exploitation, IPR & business model roadmaps	R — Document, report	M36
D7.2	Standardisation roadmap including FTO analysis	R — Document, report	M36
D7.3	Assessment of the market readiness	R — Document, report	M36
D7.4	Business and Investment Plan	R — Document, report	M36
D7.5	Report on business investments	R — Document, report	M36
D7.6	List of bottlenecks	R — Document, report	M36
<u>WP8: Cascade Funding</u>			
D8.1	Open call documents Kit & third party financing rules	R — Document, report	M13
D8.2	Open calls report – 1 st release	R — Document, report	M18
D8.3	Open calls report – 2 nd release	R — Document, report	M27
D8.4	Analytics on the submitted proposals and selected projects	R — Document, report	M33

#	Title of expected deliverable	Type of expected deliverable	Due Date
<u>WP9: Quality</u>			
D9.1	Quality Assurance Plan	R — Document, report	M3
D9.2	Monitoring & Evaluation Reports – 1 st release	R — Document, report	M12
D9.3	Monitoring & Evaluation Reports -2 nd release	R — Document, report	M24
D9.4	Monitoring & Evaluation Reports - Final release	R — Document, report	M36
<u>WP10: Dissemination and Sustainability</u>			
D10.1	Dissemination and Communication Plan – 1 st release	R — Document, report	M3
D10.2	Dissemination and Communication Plan – 2 nd release	R — Document, report	M12
D10.3	Dissemination and Communication Plan – 3 rd release	R — Document, report	M24
D10.4	Dissemination and Communication Plan - final release	R — Document, report	M36
D10.5	MoU and/or Lols signed	Other	M36

TABLE 1. WORK PACKAGES AND DELIVERABLES

Progress and performance must be measured to attest a development in the project. With few, but carefully selected indicators, it is possible to get a good overview on the progress and performance. The following table shows the initial list of indicators that are designed to measure the progress of the project.

#	Indicators name	How indicators will be measured
1	Website attractiveness	N. of unique users

#	Indicators name	How indicators will be measured
2	Planted trees	N. of planted trees
3	Market impact	N. of SMEs financed via FSTP
4	Stakeholders attractiveness	N. of signed MoUs
5	% of satisfaction among involved stakeholders	Survey among stakeholders
6	Media coverage	n. followers LinkedIn n. followers Twitter n. people watching recorded videos n. press releases n. publications n. subscribers to the newsletter
7	Level of collected data	Data records, web metrics
8	Carbon Farming Technology Platform	INNO4CFIs platform developed

TABLE 2. INITIAL PROGRESS INDICATORS TABLE

1.2 The consortium structure

The INNO4CFIs consortium consists of 14 different actors from 8 EU Countries (Italy, Belgium, Spain, Ireland, Austria, Germany, The Netherlands, Greece): public and private research institutions (Fondazione E. Amaldi, CNR, USAL, NTUA,), business networks (F6S, AINIA), SMEs specialised in different fields related to green technologies, including dissemination, communication and exploitation of results (Planet, Tredom, TreeO, Space4Good, AB Corp, Circonnect, Rancho Guarena, Novobiom).

The partners complement each other in terms of background knowledge, technical competences, and capability of new knowledge creation, business and market experiences, and expertise in commercial domains where the project innovations can be readily exploited as well as have a wide network and outreach in Europe and beyond, ensuring the project impacts are widely communicated. The best possible partners have been selected in order to actively and effectively contribute to different WPs. The consortium is very well placed along the entire green technology innovation ecosystem value chain, and a careful mix of networks, SMEs, research centres, and universities with a proven track record in both developing green technologies and assisting businesses to scale-up will be committed to the project's success.

Furthermore, each partner is located in a critical EU innovation region, allowing knowledge exchange and cross-pollination to have an even greater impact and reach. The partners interact at different levels of the value chain, providing at the required time and according to predefined agreements the optimal contributions to achieve the objectives of the project. They will share knowledge, methodology, best practices, innovative tools and technology to realize not just new technologies/products, but also innovative business models and value chains, able to improve the operational excellence in all the sectors considered by the proposal. Each partner has a distinct function and responsibility in specific project tasks, but participates in a variety of activities, bringing complementary knowledge and a genuine professional contribution to each assigned duty, as indicated below (Table 2).

Partner	Role in the project	Expertise/knowledge
FEA	Coordinator: WP1 leader	Research and technology transfer, innovation acceleration, DeepTech and SpaceTech, market-readiness and investments
Planet sas	Partner: WP3 leader	Technology developer, support to go to market phase, exploitation scenarios.
Treedom srl	Partner: WP6 leader	Validation of the business model, tree planting and exploitation scenarios
Space4Good	Partner: WP4 leader	Clean and sustainable satellite technologies, green industry, start-up and SME innovation
CNR	Partner: WP9 leader	Technical validation of the agroforestry business model, quality control and INNO4CFIs overall performance monitoring
F6S	Partner: WP8 leader	Business angels, investment in start-ups and innovative companies, entrepreneurship, business acceleration, funding
AB Corporation	Partner: WP7 leader	Exploitation strategy and business model, communication and dissemination, acceleration
Circonnect	Partner: WP10 leader	Research & Innovation, market and technical consulting, communication and dissemination, acceleration
USAL	Partner: WP5 leader	Research and development, Green technology application, carbon credit smart contract and related model, applied A.I. to the INNO4CFIs business model.

NTUA	Partner: WP2 leader	Context and market analysis, applied research, coordination of WEFE Nexus methodology and best case scenario
AINIA	Partner: technology developer	Technology developer, support to go to market phase, exploitation scenarios.
NOVOBIOM	Partner: technology developer	Validation of the business model, research and development for green technologies applications
TREEO	Partner: technology developer	Technology development, training support, forestry and carbon expertise
RGHOL	Partner: validation phase	Validation of the technology in a mixed agriculture and livestock scenario

TABLE 3: CONSORTIUM STRUCTURE

1.3 Impact of the project

INNO4CFIs has a wide impact among the Green and Carbon Farming sector, especially towards the identified following targets:

- **SMEs active in Green Technologies and Carbon Farming:** INNO4CFIs will boost the economy of the Carbon Farming Sector reinforcing the commercial know-how and capabilities of at least 40 SMEs redistributing 2 million Euro via cascade funding. Furthermore, it will implement and validate an innovative Carbon Farming Technological Platform, which will enable any Green Tech stakeholder to measure in real time various types of data (CO2 emission and savings, soil conditions, water necessity, and so on) while also optimising their resources thanks to the A.I. component. Finally, the Biodiversity Carbon Credit entrusted with blockchain technology will allow the buyers to have the certainty of one only Carbon Credit Certificate.
- **Farming communities:** Following the suggestion of the European Commission, the stakeholders analysis provided by WP10 aims to involve farmers and/or their representatives in the development of the INNO4CFIs business model, thus improving the project's impact in the farming sector (Technical Guideline on Carbon Farming, EC, page 37).
- **Investors and Venture Capitalists:** INNO4CFIs has a strong exploitation plan and aims to provide a high technological and efficient business model to the Carbon Farming Market. As a result, following the validation phase, the project will investigate investor interest in giving resources in the business model, using the strong networks of F6S, FEA, and AINIA. All of these partners will contribute to reaching the target of at least a total of 5 Memorandums of Understanding/Agreements to ensure the long-term viability of the Carbon Technology Platform developed through INNO4CFIs.
- **Public and Regional Authorities:** INNO4CFIs is in line with the European Commission Smart Specialization Strategy as well as with the Regional Smart Specialization Strategies that are supporting the INNO4CFIs initiative. It has an extensive impact at the regional, national, and European levels by providing a new business model and cascade funding, as well as

policy recommendations gathered on the ground through the stakeholder guideline (deliverable 6.3).

Short term impact	Target groups/ potential beneficiaries	Indicators (quantitative and qualitative)
Deployment of innovative solutions compared to existing technologies/solutions	SMEs, Farming Communities, Investors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Inventory of the success cases and go-to-business scenario ● Report on Needs of low and moderate innovative regions ● KPIs inventory
Uptake of technologically and economically reliable and viable solutions on the market	SMEs, Farming Communities, Investors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Carbon credit recommendation system based on ethical and social AI. ● Low-power DLT P2P CC smart contract execution environment

TABLE 4: SHORT TERM IMPACTS AND RELATED INDICATORS

Medium-term impact	Target groups/ potential beneficiaries	Indicators (quantitative and qualitative)
Creating new market opportunities for EU companies	SMEs and start-ups, Investors and Venture Capitalists, EU companies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● KPIs assessment report ● Biodiversity Carbon Credit Report ● End users questionnaires ● Stakeholders guidelines: design establishment and evaluation of the INNO4CFIs Carbon Credit Model
Reinforcing the capacity of regions to invest, joining forces around shared S3 investment	Companies, research organisations, regional authorities, European public and private entities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● End users questionnaires ● Number of local participants trained

Medium-term impact	Target groups/ potential beneficiaries	Indicators (quantitative and qualitative)
priorities (interregional investments)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● KPIs assessment report
Innovation diffusion	Companies, research organisations, regional authorities, European public and private entities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Exploitation, IPR & business model roadmaps ● Business and Investment Plan ● Report on business investments

TABLE 5: MEDIUM-TERM IMPACTS AND RELATED INDICATORS

Long-term impact	Target groups/ potential beneficiaries	Indicators (quantitative and qualitative)
Reinforcing/reshaping EU value chains whilst increasing EU competitiveness in global markets	European Union, European private and public entities, municipalities, end users, policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● MoU and/or LoIs signed ● Monitoring & Evaluation Reports
Unlocking the innovation potential of EU regions/countries	Companies, including SMEs, especially in the participating regions and countries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Number of projects funded through the calls for proposals ● Number of 8 experts selected
Contributing to the European Green Deal objectives	European citizens, end users, regulating bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Number of trees and biological species planted ● Agroforestry project design
Positive impact on environment, health, climate, social and economy	Companies, research organisations, regional authorities, European public and private entities, end users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Number of trees and biological species planted ● Agroforestry project design ● End users questionnaires
Economic growth and job creation	Companies, research organisations, regional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Biodiversity Carbon Credit Report

Long-term impact	Target groups/ potential beneficiaries	Indicators (quantitative and qualitative)
	authorities, European public and private entities, end users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholders guidelines: design establishment and evaluation of the INNO4CFIs Carbon Credit Model

TABLE 6: LONG-TERM IMPACTS AND RELATED INDICATORS

2. Project management approach

Overall, project management encompasses technical, financial and administrative coordination as well as the supervision of various activities within the project. To manage a project of the size and complexity of INNO4CFIs, a professional and flexible management structure is vital. Transparent decision making processes are required to both encourage project development and foster confidence amongst the project consortium. Clear and pragmatic decision-making and communication pathways and prompt reporting mechanisms are necessary.

2.1 Overall Management strategy

Quality and risk management are the external walls. They permeate all activities of the project and act as safeguards. Quality is assured and risks are assessed for both project products and project management practices. All activities end with the communication of decisions, changes and actions to consortium members and the European Commission. These are the activities which bound project management for INNO4CFIs as it is shown in the figure below.

FIGURE 1. PROJECT MANAGEMENT ARCHITECTURE

The core activities which ensure the project stays on track are the scope, cost and schedule management. Procurement management describes how to handle purchases, while staff management defines the needs in terms of people, their roles and who is going to fill those roles. The relationship between coordinator and members of the consortium is that of partnership and not subcontracting. As such, the Coordinator does not have the authority to impose procurement and staffing practices or plans to partners. Individual partners manage these issues internally. Additionally, different overarching institutional policies and national laws regulations place different demands which make these issues best left to partners to manage. Nonetheless, they have an impact on the core activities of project management, thus claiming a place in the project management architecture. The core activities of project management lead to decisions and changes in both the work of the project and its management. These are managed through change management which feed into communications management ensuring information reaches all appropriate audiences. The quality management contributes in establishing the relevant to the project quality control and quality assurance activities for ensuring an efficient collaboration among the consortium partners and delivery of project results, whereas the risk management is necessary for providing the process and techniques for the evaluation and control of potential project risks, focusing on their precautionary diagnosis and handling.

2.2 Project management structure

The INNO4CFIs project management takes into account all the partners' interests and expertise, including transparent activities, in order to ensure an effective project's time-plan and execution.

The project management of INNO4CFIs is composed as shown in table 6:

<u>Roles</u>	<u>Supervisor</u>	<u>Responsibilities</u>
INNO4CFIs Steering Committee	Coordinator and one senior representative for each partner	The consortium's decision-making and arbitration board of the project. The SC supervises the development of planned activities and defines the overall project strategy, considering long-term interests of the project and fulfilment of the Grant Agreement (GA) commitments
INNO4CFIs Technical Committee	Coordinator and WP leaders	The Technical Committee responsibilities are to report on progresses towards project's objectives, monitor technical progresses and achievements, take corrective measures/contingency plans, review internal work plans (especially for activities across WPs), ensure deliverables/reports are of good technical quality/timely issued, discuss about common exploitation/dissemination actions and other innovation-related activities
Project coordinator	Eleonora Lombardi	The Coordinator will be responsible for maintaining oversight of project's finances, project partners' financial statements, receive/distribute pre-financing and grant payments to partners, carry on the scientific/technical supervision of the project and coordinating the work planned, monitor/review the completion of milestones/deliverables and formally submit deliverables/periodic reports to the EC, gather cost statements/audit certificates and coordinate payments, supervise any other legal/contractual/ethical/financial and administrative management of the Consortium, including maintenance of the Consortium Agreement (CA), chair the Steering (SC) and Technical Committee (TC) meetings.
Project manager	Valerio Roscani, - Lead project manager and Fondazione E. Amaldi staff in support.	The project manager will be responsible for the organisation of meetings/teleconferences/other related activities in order to facilitate communications within/between various WPs, including support to minutes collection, periodically

		<p>monitor the use of resources/expenditures of partners, prepare and post-process of EC reports from the consortium-side (including support in implementing recommendations from the EC), feed/maintain an intranet and other tools to facilitate internal communication, create external communication procedures/templates, ensure EC requirements are met, support the communication and promote synergies within the consortium.</p>
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TABLE 7: ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

2.3 Management Procedures

Project and quality management activities will ensure the proper implementation of the project plan and the realisation of its objectives. Decisions will normally be taken by the responsible team members based on the work to be performed, as stated in the Partnership agreement and the Detailed description of the project, individual Work Package or Task plans. During the project the participating organisations will have to reach an agreement and resolve various technical and scientific issues. This agreement/resolution can be reached by informal contact as a first step, followed by official verification by means of e-mail, letter or minutes. Technical issues/conflicts within the given contractual commitments that do not involve alterations in contract, in budget and in the overall focus will be initially handled on the Work Package basis. In the event of a project conflict among partners, the latter should attempt to resolve conflicts among themselves in good will and an amicable manner given the professional nature of the organisations involved and maintaining the project's success as the ultimate goal.

If the dispute cannot be resolved, partners will escalate the issue according to the following principles:

- The WP leader will be informed of the issue/conflict that came up.
- The WP leader will arrange and lead a discussion among the WP team. In case of an agreement the PC will be notified as no further actions are needed.
- In case an agreement is not reached the PC will then intervene and organise a meeting/discussion among the responsible partners.
- In case the issue is solved and requires a change in the Grant Agreement, the Project Coordinator will notify the EC's Project Adviser. Otherwise, an extraordinary meeting of partners will be organised in order to resolve the issue and take the final decision, which must be accepted by all involved partners. The rules of voting in this case are described below.

Conflict is not expected to be a significant factor since the roles of each partner have been well defined, so as to avoid any misunderstandings that might occur later in the project. The resolution of problems and conflicts are handled systematically. Establishing a good working relationship among the project team members is a prerequisite for the quick resolution of problems and issues. Conflicts resolution are based on the principle that any dispute should be resolved by consent and as near the source as possible, thus, conflicts on a local sphere are managed by the people involved (e.g. a dispute between the partners engaged in a WP should be addressed by that WP team). Conflicts which cannot be solved internally are taken through a "principled negotiation" process that is focused on optimising outcomes and maximising the benefits of all parties involved.

In case of conflicts arising within the consortium regarding the carrying out of the project or other matters related to the project itself, the following steps are taken:

- The parties will try to resolve the conflict issue amicably between them.
- If a conflict cannot be resolved within the local sphere, it is raised to the PC; for conflict resolution in a technical aspect, the PC is in charge of proposing an alternative. If this is agreed, the issue is solved.
- If this attempt fails the question will be brought to the first scheduled meeting of the SC, or in case of urgency, an ad hoc meeting of the SC will be called for by the Project Coordinator, upon request of a SC member;
- The question will be discussed within the SC, and the Project Coordinator will try to solve it by consensus; the SC will decide which procedure will be followed, and the corresponding correction measures that should be taken. The participant that provokes the conflict will declare acceptance of the procedure and the corrective measures.
- If the conflict cannot be resolved, the PC declares the participant “not in line” with the project execution and the Consortium will ask for a contract termination for the participant concerned, with the contractually stated consequences. The EC Project Adviser will be immediately notified of the situation and of the measures to be taken in order to solve it. An appropriate review of the work plan will be suggested by the PC, approved by the SC and sent to the commission for acceptance.
- In case it is decided (by the PC or SC) that a conflict resolution will involve a voting procedure among partners, a majority of the 70% will be required for the decision to go ahead (10 out of 14 partners).

3. Quality Expectations

The present chapter presents the expectations of the project consortium with reference to the INNO4CFIs deliverables and activities as well as the expectations relevant to the project management.

3.1 Quality of the project implementation

INNO4CFIs has a twofold objective:

1. To promote reforestation/agroforestry practices to increase CO₂ uptake while promoting crucial environmental co-benefits such as sustainable freshwater production, dry-land and soil restoration and, biodiversity promotion.
2. Financing highly innovative technologies promoted by SMEs located in i3-eligible countries (EU27), through a cascade funding scheme which will finance minimum 40 enterprises. The promotion of Carbon Farming practices will be the focus of the proposal, thanks to the expertise developed by the consortium through the H2020 Hydrousa project and the PRIMA Nexus project. Through the combination of the WEFE Nexus Methodology and the technological maturation of the involved technologies, the design of systemic solutions balancing the interdependencies between water, energy, food and the environment, as well as the implementation and financing of Carbon Farming projects will be ensured.

The partners agree that this overall objective shall always be in the forefront of all decisions to be taken. The partners therefore might decide to prioritise certain activities over others which have a higher impact in relation to the achievement of the objectives. Quality in the project means that the achievement of the objectives might be more important even if it means, for example, postponing a deadline or changing some aspects of an activity.

Six specific objectives of the project are:

1. Implementing the stakeholder analysis according to the SME and Start-up needs of the identified regions using the WEFE Nexus methodology.
2. Demonstrating and validating the achievement of TRL8 for the Carbon Farming Technology Platform.
3. Design and implementation of a low-power P2P platform equipped with Self-Sovereign Digital Id (SSID) and Smart contracts for the secure execution and management of Carbon Credit transactions.
4. Validation of INNO4CFIs business model.
5. Promote access to cascade funding for the implementation of highly innovative carbon farming technologies in the territories selected by the project, thus increasing their competitive advantage.
6. Evaluate the sustainability of the INNO4CFIs business model.

3.2 Quality of project deliverables

The deliverables of INNO4CFIs may be classified into tangible deliverables such as reports, publications, manuals, methodology, plans, printed and electronically available promotional material, as well as intangible deliverables in the form of organised events (trainings, conferences, seminars, info days, etc.), developed and launched innovation platforms, established Creativity Centres, integrative approaches in continuing education, competition for best student ideas, etc.

A common quality expectation for all deliverables is their relevance to reach the overall objective and the specific objectives, with a further focus on their development in an efficient and effective manner.

3.2.1 Quality of document based deliverables

A consistent and common format for all document based deliverables (word document, powerpoint presentations) is to be followed by all partners using templates provided in the Dissemination and Communication Plan.

- Annex I – Deliverable template
- Annex II – Powerpoint presentation template (SlideMaster)

Four more templates are also provided for review purposes:

- Annex III - Deliverable Quality Assurance Check
- Annex IV - Participant Feedback Form
- Annex V - Event Report Templates
- Annex VI - Risk Monitoring Sheet

Those templates will be suggested to the SC members in order to ensure a common appearance of deliverables as well as to ensure that a minimum amount of information will appear consistently in all documents produced by the project. This is not relevant to deliverables that by their nature need to have a different format (i.e. project brochures, newsletters).

When partners produce studies and publications as deliverable, as well as communication activities related to the action (including media relations, conferences, etc.) they are obliged to display the European flag and a funding statement on the cover or the first page. Moreover, they must use the following disclaimer on the inner pages: “Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA) - Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

3.2.2 Quality of INNO4CFIs events

All events with external stakeholders organised by the project should be organised professionally. The organisers should provide in due time a full information package to the participants including the draft agenda, letter of invitation and a note on the logistics (informing about travel arrangements, venue, suggested hotels, etc.). Time for preparation activities depends on the type of event e.g. several months for conference and several weeks for trainings. This will be defined in separate action plans by task leaders.

The meeting organisers ensure smooth registration processes (including list of attendees – Annex D) and the implementation of the meetings respecting appropriate time for event sessions and breaks as well as the availability of all necessary materials (e.g. training and promotional material). The organisers will also ensure the recording of minutes of the meetings in a concise style including a list of action points. Where appropriate (e.g. for trainings, seminars) also feedback forms will be distributed among participants (Annex E) and event reports related to feedback forms will be prepared

by organisers (Annex F). Powerpoint presentations should be prepared using appropriate templates (Annex C).

The partners shall inform the public, press and media (internet included) of the event which must visibly indicate “Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA) - Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.” as well as the European flag and funding statement.

Posters, roll-up and other promotional materials shall be displayed during the event. Each event will be documented by various materials as described in the table below and if applicable.

<u>Type of event</u>	<u>Materials</u>	<u>Available through</u>	
		<u>INNO4CFIs website</u>	<u>Social Networks</u>
Events, workshops and seminars	News/social media posts		
	Agenda		
	List of participants*		
	Report		
	Gallery		
	Presentations**		
Kick off and SC meetings	News		
	Agenda		
	List of participants*		
	Report		
	Gallery		
	Presentations**		
	News		

TABLE 8. INNO4CFIs EVENT MATERIALS

*Name and affiliation will be visible, all personal data will be hidden

**Upon the approval of the presenter and if applicable

3.2.3 Quality of promotion materials

Communication and dissemination activities of the project will adhere to the Dissemination and Communication Plan (D10.1, D10.2, D10.3, D10.4) of the project. All promotional materials will reflect the visual identity of the project. The partner Circonnect is responsible for design of all promotional material. The draft version will be sent to all partners for comments and suggestions, before printing, publishing and distribution.

The materials will be disseminated by all project partners at events which are relevant to reach the project's target group (i.e. not only events organised by the project itself, but also general events with a focus on research, technological development and innovation).

3.2.4 Quality of websites and other electronic tools

The project envisages setting up the public INNO4CFIs web-site (<https://www.inno4cfis.eu/>) and different social media profiles, which are described in the Dissemination and Communication Plan (D10.1). INNO4CFIs is represented on the social media platforms LinkedIn, X (Twitter) to share information and engage with relevant stakeholders. All representation tools will be continuously updated by the partners and are intended to effectively communicate the results of the project.

AB Corporation will be responsible for setting up and maintaining the INNO4CFIs website with all information and materials received from project partners and will perform analogous activities on the social media pages. Moreover, all partners are asked to promote INNO4CFIs project on their websites and other media tools (such as: Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn profiles/groups, newsletters, etc.) by providing short description of the project, logo and link to INNO4CFIs website. The INNO4CFIs platform can be accessed by all partners depending on their assigned tasks and roles. It will be the single point of reference for the project documentation and communication among partners. Circonnect will set up and maintain the INNO4CFIs platform. All tools will be implemented with high performance, good functionality and stability, emphasising the maximum reach and awareness of the target audience.

3.2.5 Quality of project management

The project management structure was established at the project's Kick-off meeting to ensure effectiveness, decisiveness, flexibility and quality of work. It involves the Coordinator, the Project Manager, a Steering Committee (SC), Quality Assurance Project Team (QAPT, 13 members; Eleonora Lombardi, Alessandro Zecca, Elisabetta Meconcelli, Federico Franciamore, Admira Boshnyaku, Andrea Boffi, Gianni Della Rocca, Vanessa Vivian Wabitsch, Javier Parra, Stepisnik Tadej, Erika Albergo, Joaquim Halen, Javier Sanchez). The Steering Committee will review the activities and decide on any necessary contingency measures in reorganisation tasks and resources – as usual with a strong focus on the project impact. The project management will be transparent and flexible but also strict enough to ensure the implementation of the project activities in order to achieve the project's objectives. Each partner is equally and independently responsible for assigned activities, money use and reporting. Contact persons have the responsibility for the local management.

The Project Management Strategy document, shared as output of Milestone 1 of INNO4CFIs, reports all the needed information for an efficient and performing implementation of the project.

4. Internal monitoring

Internal monitoring will be carried out by all partners, including self-evaluation by using the Work Plan, budget and cash flow tables, SC meetings, monitoring visits of the QAPT and questionnaires/satisfaction surveys of target groups (e.g. participants of dissemination and training events).

4.1 Project quality assurance strategy

The internal quality assurance in INNO4CFIs includes four levels of quality control (1) Deliverable authors, tasks, and WP leaders, (2) Deliverable reviewers, (3) Coordinator level, and (4) Steering Committee level and final approval:

1. Deliverable authors, task and WP leaders: The 1st level corresponds to the activity level. The presentation of deliverables and activities of the project are a joint responsibility of the Task Leader and WP leader. It shall guarantee the quality and timeliness of the deliverable as identified in Application Form and action plan (modified and agreed by the SC on six-month basis). The “final draft deliverable” should be presented to the partners at least 15 days from the due date, to ensure a proper timing.
2. Deliverable reviewers: The 2nd level of control corresponds to the review from the partners, which have 15 days to check and comment on the deliverable. The reviewer should be indicated in the introductory table of each deliverable according to the deliverable template, under the line the “reviewers”. In case profound disagreements between reviewers and Task leaders arise, the 3rd level control of the deliverables will allow the project coordinator to have a final say – with the possibility to involve the rest of the consortium if deemed necessary.
3. Steering Committee level (only if necessary): if a draft deliverable has not passed the 2nd level control and there are disagreements between the deliverable authors and the reviewers, the Steering Committee will take the necessary corrective actions in order to come up with a shared result.
4. Coordinator level and final approval: The 3rd level control is done by the Project Coordinator. It shall be possible to include a deliverable in the project reports even if its formal approval is still pending, if it has passed the 2nd and 3rd level of control without profound disagreements as then no major alterations are to be expected. It is expected that the partners will also establish internal quality control mechanisms, i.e. the contact persons will always check the output of his/her project team before sending documents to the review or before uploading them on the INNO4CFIs website.

4.2 Quality responsibilities

Different roles are identified with reference to the development of the project activities and in particular the project quality assurance procedures. Different responsibilities are associated with the different roles.

4.2.1 Task Leader (responsible for the deliverable)

The partner in charge for the deliverable is responsible for:

- coordinating the development of the deliverable(s) according to the deliverable template;
- Uploading it in the related Google Drive folder of the project ;
- assigning parts of the work to other partners involved in the activity;

- coordinating the work of other partners involved in the activity, providing guidance when necessary;
- aligning the contributions of the other partners involved in the activity, in order to produce the deliverable;
- the submission of the draft deliverable to the WP leader (1st level control), the partners (2nd level control) and the coordinator (3rd level control);
- implementing the suggestions of the reviewers (2nd level), assigning certain amendments as appropriate;
- sending the amended draft deliverable.

Moreover, the task leader will report to the WP Leader for any problems occurring during the implementation of the activity and they will cooperate with the WP Leader and other partners in the same WP in order to ensure the activity's progress in conformity with other activities and that any cross-activity inputs and outputs are being delivered as foreseen by the WP description (respecting any changes approved by the Steering Committee as recorded in the respective minutes).

4.2.2 Reviewers (other partners involved in the activity, co-authors)

Other partners, co-authors of the deliverable, will be responsible for:

- On general terms, revising the contents of the deliverable;
- the production of their part in the deliverable according to the Task Leader's instructions;
- making sure that their written contributions comply with the Deliverable Template so that to ensure that the Task Leader will be able to put all contributions together in the desirable format;
- providing to the Task Leader all the complementary information regarding their work (i.e. references, bibliography, methodologies used, contact details of people interviewed etc.);

4.2.3 WP Leader

WP Leaders will be responsible for:

- delivery of up-to-date information on the WP progress, making sure that all activities are in the time frame defined in the Work Plan;
- coordinating the Work Package and ensuring that all the activities are contributing to the WP's objectives;
- cooperating with the Task Leaders and the coordinator in ensuring that all of the contributing partners are smoothly cooperating with a view to accomplish the WP's objectives and that any cross-WP inputs and outputs are being delivered as foreseen by the project description;
- sending alerts on time to remind about submission deadlines and the procedures to be followed and provides input and suggestions to the Task Leaders of the WP during the development of the relevant deliverables;
- providing to the Task Leaders comments and suggestions on the draft deliverables (1st level control);
- cooperating with the Task Leaders in ensuring the implementation of the suggestions of the QAPT team and Project Coordinator (2nd and 3rd level control),
- verifying the satisfactory implementation of the recommendations.

4.2.4 Quality Assurance Project Team

The Quality Assurance Project Team is coordinated by the QAPT Coordinator, as agreed by the Steering Committee at the kick-off meeting. The QAPT has the following responsibilities:

- is responsible for the Quality Assurance exercise of deliverables ;
- receives each draft deliverable from the Task Leader and provides feedback accordingly ;
- sends feedback for review of deliverable to the Task Leader and WP leader ;
- verifies the satisfactory implementation of the recommendations and comments;
- cooperates with the Project Coordinator on general issues related to the level of quality of the project's deliverables as appropriate.

4.2.5 Project Coordinator

The Project Coordinator, Fondazione E. Amaldi (FEA), will be responsible for:

- cooperating with the QAPT and the WP Leaders on all matters arising relevant to ensuring the quality of the project's deliverables;
- accepting the deliverable or providing final comments to the Task Leaders and WP Leaders (3rd level control);
- cooperating with the WP Leaders in order to ensure that all WPs are progressing in conformity with each other and that any cross-WP inputs and outputs are being delivered as foreseen by the WP description;
- informing the QAPT, the WP Leaders and the Task Leaders of any changes in the Consortium Agreement and/or Grant Agreement, and the related Work Plan or any implicit changes in the implementation of the project that may affect the timing or the content of the relevant deliverables;
- officially submitting all approved deliverables.

4.2.6 Steering Committee

The Steering Committee, constituted by the Coordinator and one senior representative per partner, is the decision-making body of the project. In relation to quality procedure, the SC will be responsible in case of disagreement in the deliverables contents.

4.3 Quality feedback by the target groups

The satisfaction of stakeholders, beneficiaries and end users will also be investigated. It will take into account a variety of information from different sources using visits, interviews, questionnaires to target groups and consultation with the project beneficiaries.

In order to allow the impact assessment of the project activities, a template for participants feedback for different meetings / events was developed (Annex IV).

Furthermore, a specific event report template (Annex V) has been developed which is to be filled by project partners (organisers) for all INNO4CFIs events (workshops, info days, trainings, etc. – except SC meetings). Report will include summary review of statistical data with graphical presentations collected by participants about their satisfaction.

4.4 Risk Management

As part of the internal quality management, a regular risk assessment will be carried and reviewed out during the Steering Committee meetings (Risk brainstorming) which shall lead to corrective actions and potential adaptations of the Work Plan based on a sound process.

The risk management strategy addresses issues that could potentially endanger the achievement of the overall goal of the project and its objectives considering potential financial risks (overspending and underspending), timing (postponing of activities/deliverables), performance risks (project management), and sustainability of the project results. The main aim will be to provide a sound assessment, to anticipate challenges in a systematic way and to minimise the potentially negative overall impact.

The identification and assessment of new risks is a joint responsibility of all project partners who have to communicate them to the Project Coordinator and the Steering Committee, eventually suggesting possible interventions and solutions, as soon as they get aware of those risks. In particular, partners may think of preventive actions (avoiding that the risk occurs) and corrective actions (decreasing the severity and impact), specifying also the resources that would be needed. The Steering Committee may react in several ways, ranging from the simple acceptance of the situation in the case of negligible risks, to the enforcement of a mitigation plan including alternatives, workarounds and the proposed corrective actions that will make the risk consequences acceptable for the consortium.

The proper allocation of resources to the project by the individual project partners is of utmost importance. There are several possible risks connected: the delay of the project implementation as defined in the project work plan; the rushed implementation of the work plan with low quality; an underspending during the project implementation (also causing a shift in the headings' ratio), meaning that the project timetable is followed with reference to technical deliverables, yet the relevant expenditures are not timely invoiced or validated, etc. The project partners all have to ensure that they allocate the needed resources to the project, both human and financial.

4.4.1 Practical approach to risk identification

The first step in project risk management is to identify the risks that are present in a project. The risks should furthermore be identified as early as possible in order to deal with them properly and to think about corrective and/or preventive actions. In order to identify and monitor the risks within INNO4CFIs project, a risks monitoring sheet has been developed including the information on corrective and/or preventive actions (Annex G). It should be kept in mind that this is not a one-time activity. As the project progresses, new risks may evolve or become known while others may no longer be relevant.

During the meetings the potential risks have been identified and categorised according to the work packages to make the mitigation part easier to manage.

The Risk Severity Matrix has been created, highlighting in red, dark red and purple the results of the risk analysis that clearly indicate a reduced quality of the project.

Probability of Occurrence	Has happened often	4	4	8	12	16
	There has been “close call” situations	3	3	6	9	12
	Has happened occasionally	2	2	4	6	8
	Very unlikely/rare	1	1	2	3	4
		Impact	1	2	3	4
		Low	Medium	High	Critical	

Figure 2: Risk Severity Matrix

4.4.2 Risk/Uncertainties monitoring procedure

- WP Leaders (or Task Leaders) **identify possible risks/uncertainties** in their WP and fill in the template (Annex VI).
- **The risk monitoring sheets (Annex G) are communicated** to QAPT Team + WP9 Leader (CNR) + Project coordinator (FEA).
- QAPT Team + WP9 Leader (CNR) + Project Coordinator (FEA) **register, analyse and prioritise** risks/uncertainties.
- QAPT Team + WP9 Leader (CNR) + Project Coordinator (FEA) **plan and implement risk responses.**

Steering Committee meetings will be used also to organise risk brainstorming sessions based on the Annex G template. After each Steering Committee meeting this template will be updated by the QAPT Team.

4.4.3 Risk Response development

For each risk, there are four response strategies that one can choose from:

- **Avoid:** In some cases, risk avoidance is possible by making a change to the project management plan. Some examples include extending or shortening the schedule, changing the project strategy, or reducing scope.
- **Transfer:** Risk transfer involves passing the risk to a third party. This doesn't change or eliminate the risk, it simply gives another party the responsibility to manage the risk. Examples of risk transfer include insurance and guarantees.
- **Mitigate:** Risk mitigation means to reduce the probability and/or impact of a risk event. Examples of risk mitigation include safety training and simplifying processes.
- **Accept:** Risk acceptance is when the SC decides not to change the project management plan to deal with the risk or is unable to identify any other risk response strategies for a risk event. This strategy can be passive where the project team decides to just deal with the risk if it occurs. Or it can be active where the project team has a contingency reserve allocated and plan in place in case the risk occurs.

Table 8 shows a preliminary identification of possible risks that will be monitored and updated using the risk monitoring sheet throughout the project.

Description of risk (Low/Medium/High)	WPs involved	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Lack of overall coordination Likelihood: low	WP1	Effective coordination is ensured by the managerial structure and through the project work plan. In case of unforeseen events, other experienced persons at the coordinating organisation or at other partners can take over coordination tasks.
Consortium disruption Likelihood: low	WP1	All partners have experience and proven track records in large projects. All are motivated to reach the project objectives, which have been defined in the common interest of all partners. Any partner not adhering to this common interest will be excluded from the project.
Conflicts in the consortium Likelihood: low	WP1	A comprehensive Consortium Agreement will be formulated by all partners. The PM will maintain an easily searchable record of all relevant correspondence among partners to aid the coordinator in resolving conflicts. All partners have a track record of solving emergent problems in a collegial spirit.
Delays in deliverables Likelihood: medium	WP2, WP4, WP1, WP6, WP3, WP5, WP8, WP9, WP7, WP10	A system will be implemented to spot delays of critical deliverables (those that link to milestones) early; mitigating actions will be discussed with WP-partners involved to keep the project on time. Partners in WPs will appoint project personnel in time. When they possess spare capacity, failure of one will be mitigated quickly by others.
A partner leaves the project Likelihood: low	WP2, WP4, WP1, WP6, WP3, WP5, WP8, WP9, WP7, WP10	Partner's expectations will be continuously verified in order to ensure their commitment to the project. In case it will happen, the project management board will analyse 2 main options: 1) the substitution of the partner by another one of similar characteristics 2) the assumption and redistribution of tasks among the high number of partners of the project.
Low involvement of stakeholders Likelihood: medium	WP10	During the first four months of the project, the consortium will contact all the relevant stakeholders (e.g., public institutions, business support organisations, etc.) to ensure the consolidation of a database of contacts, which will be engaged via events and interactive workshops. Success cases on the potentiality of the European programmes will be

		disseminated with the assistance of national clusters, through posts, social media, video, brochure.
Decision support system doesn't produce the expected results Likelihood: medium	WP2, WP4, WP1, WP6, WP3, WP5, WP9, WP8, WP7, WP10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In depth analysis of context and understanding of bottlenecks to be solved via our business model. • Wide approach to the analysis of factors related from a financial perspective that will take advantage from the multi-actor approach in order to select the correct indicators. • In depth analysis of existing best practices and sharing methods.
Poor results of evaluation Likelihood: low	WP9	The management structures are prepared to launch severe corrective measures if major failures are detected. Earlier actions are encouraged to avoid this.
Call procedures too complex leading to low level of applicants Likelihood: low	WP8	Simple mechanisms to connect and ask questions to the project team will be in place. Clear guidelines to be provided, and a first draft of the application package has been provided in the Annex of the Application Form. Regular monitoring of applicant activity in line with revising the promotional campaign will be done as needed to increase applications.
Low level of interest from SMEs and startups in applying Likelihood: low	WP8	Regular monitoring in the number of applications received against targets to pick up early warnings of low application, with promotion and dissemination activities in place to reach and engage potential applicants.
Difficulty to engage external evaluators for the proposals Likelihood: low	WP8	A public call will be issued to engage external evaluators for the proposals and it will be promoted on all the social media and channels available within the consortium (official project pages as well as consortium partner ones). In addition, an invitation will be sent specifically to an internal F6S database of more than 100 professional evaluators with a strong track record and high response rate to such calls.
Inefficient evaluation process Likelihood: low	WP8	<p>The contract will indicate a working timeline:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Onboarding date/time 2. Time period to evaluate 3. Time period for consensus meetings 4. Time period to approve Evaluation Summary Reports <p>All of this will be legally binding and evaluators should be available during the stipulated dates and adhere to the deadlines.</p>

<p>Delay in the implementation of the FSTP instrument by the awarded SME or start-up Likelihood: medium</p>	<p>WP8</p>	<p>The partners involved in the WP8 will closely monitor to identify and resolve potential issues as soon as they appear. As part of the application form, the partners will also include a risk assessment on the part of awarded SMEs (as part of their application for funding), thus they would be able to have mitigation measures in place if delays occur.</p>
<p>IPR issues not sorted, e.g., Lack of IP strategies to ensure long-term sustainability Likelihood: low</p>	<p>WP7</p>	<p>IPR related to the project are limited and the exploitation model based on openness of the project's processes. A first draft of the GDPR statement has been already produced and attached in the Annex of the AF. IPR exploitation workshop webinars aim at fostering discussion on this topic with expert participation.</p>
<p>Delays in the set-up of the living labs Likelihood: medium</p>	<p>WP6</p>	<p>A close monitoring system will be set up to detect possible delays in the recruitment of technicians promptly. Mitigating actions will be planned together with the WP partners.</p>
<p>Delays in the implementation of the SME self Assessment Tool Likelihood: low</p>	<p>WP2</p>	<p>NTUA, USAL, Planet, CNR, Treedom all have previous EU projects experience (Horizon2020, LIFE and, PRIMA programs) in the application of the NEXUS methodology. Their knowhow, together with the deep knowledge of the market of the consortium members, will allow them to set up a proper strategy to build the SME assessment tool on time.</p>
<p>Difficulties in implementing the Earth Observation system Likelihood: medium</p>	<p>WP4</p>	<p>A dedicated strategy built via the experience of the WP leader Space4Goods will be implemented in the initial phase of the WP4 (M6). Moreover, regular calls will be set up among the technical partners thus enhancing internal dialogue and to avoid shortcomings.</p>
<p>Challenges in implementing the smart contract system for green certificates Likelihood: medium</p>	<p>WP5</p>	<p>The long lasting experience of WP leader USAL in supporting and developing blockchain systems for several businesses will allow the consortium to build a monitoring and implementation strategy based on comparative analysis and execution of environmental smart contracts. The business partners will also support the application of the strategy during the validation process.</p>
<p>Smart Contract Immutability: the code of a deployed smart contract cannot be altered. This immutability means that design flaws or changes in</p>	<p>WP5</p>	<p>Utilise Upgradable Design Patterns: While not every situation allows for it, some smart contract designs can leverage patterns like the "Proxy Pattern" that allow for certain levels of upgradeability. Before deploying, it's crucial to thoroughly review and test smart contracts to minimise the need for changes. In case modifications become unavoidable, having</p>

<p>requirements cannot be addressed directly, potentially leading to project delays as new smart contracts must be developed and deployed from scratch. Likelihood: medium</p>		<p>a strategy for migrating to a new contract (e.g., transferring state/data to a new contract) can also be planned in advance.</p>
<p>Agroforestry project designed delayed Likelihood: medium</p>	<p>WP6</p>	<p>All the partners involved in the validation and testing phases as well as in the implementation of agroforestry projects have been working together for several years. Therefore, a country specific strategy will be implemented, thus building the agroforestry project according to the regional specific needs and challenges and therefore avoiding potential delays.</p>
<p>Consortium partner(s) run out of funds due to overspend or reallocation of FSTP funding Likelihood: medium</p>	<p>WP2, WP4, WP1, WP6, WP3, WP5, WP9, WP8, WP7, WP10</p>	<p>Consortium members are responsible for monitoring their own finances, with regular financial reporting led by the consortium lead to ensure visibility and ultimately mitigate budgetary challenges. In the event of an overspend by the partner(s) the consortium lead will discuss possible options for agreement (and/or escalation to EC as required) by the consortium.</p>

TABLE 9: FORESEEN CRITICAL RISKS

5. External Monitoring

External monitoring of the project will be performed by CNR. An independent Auditor will be appointed by the consortium and will perform the independent external quality assessment planned at mid-term and at the end of the project. The auditor will be chosen among at least 3 different offers according to the best value for money/quality of work criteria.

CNR performs three types of monitoring, based on deliverable achievement:

- Preventive (in the first project year)
- Advisory (after the first project year)
- Control (after the end of the project – sustainability check)

The monitoring by CNR includes the assessment of various aspects of project implementation, such as **relevance** (is project still relevant in terms of its goals and achievements), **efficiency** (are the activities in work-packages done on time), **effectiveness** (how well are project specific objectives met), **impact** (at the level of departments, faculty, university, etc.) and **sustainability** (what would stay after the project is finished).

Apart from the monitoring from CNR, the partner will additionally subcontract the external audit agency for the purpose of the establishment of indicators and measuring tools linked to FEA, that will choose among at least 3 different offers following the criteria best value for money/quality of work. This section will be updated in the upcoming updated versions, since FEA will take in charge the selection of the External Quality Assessment.

6. Effort and Cost management

The Project Coordinator with the support of the Financial Manager is responsible for managing and reporting on the project's budget and effort consumption at the project level to the European Commission throughout the duration of the project. During the internal quarterly, interim and annual progress reports, the Project Coordinator collects and presents the project's effort and cost performance for the preceding period to the EC Project Adviser and Financial Officer. Performance is measured comparing actual consumption against planned. The Project Coordinator supports sound financial management by presenting the consortium with options for getting the project back on budget, but it is not responsible for accounting for cost and effort deviations. Each partner is solely responsible for the financial management and expenditures towards the European Commission.

6.1 Effort and cost management approach

Effort and costs for INNO4CFIs will be managed at the Work Package Structure (WPS). The financial performance of the project will be measured and managed through comparisons between the actual comparison and the effort calendar and cost baselines. Activity effort is detailed at the task level and costs at the WP level. To avoid confusion and complications due to conflicts between National and European Union reporting rules, all efforts are to be reported in whole hours. Euro amounts are to be reported in two decimals.

Effort and cost variances of +/- 10% in the cost and effort performance indexes will change the status of the cost to cautionary. Cost variances of +/- 20% in the cost and effort performance indexes will change the status of the cost to an alert stage. These will serve as input to Risk Assessment and may require corrective action by the Project Coordinator in order to bring the cost and/or effort performance variations below the alert level. Corrective actions will require a project change request and must be approved before they can be included within the scope of the project.

The following reports are established:

- Interim Progress Reports (M18)
- Final Reports (M36)

In addition, the PC is updated internally on the project progress status on a yearly basis, via an internal progress reports, i.e. effort resource consumption .xls files received by all partners, and the activity bulleted reports provided by the WP Leaders.

6.2 Guidelines for Unplanned Expenses

The EU Grants detailed budget tables mentioned in the Grant Agreement detail a budget for each partner and for each task or activity in INNO4CFIs. Any effort or cost allocation which deviates from this plan presents an unplanned expense. In general terms, unplanned expenses are not allowed. However, due to the realities of implementing a project, there is the possibility that reasonable and justifiable expenses contributing to the project and not contradicting the rules of the project may be eligible.

If a partner has a cost which they believe falls under this category, they must obtain permission from the Steering Committee before incurring the cost. To do so, they need to discuss the issue with WPL. If they concur, they should email the PC with a justification to the cost requesting from the PC to obtain approval. Following due diligence, the PC may reject the justification and inform the partner or accept

it and forward the justification to the Financial Officer of the European Commission. Once the PC receives a response from the Financial Officer he/she will inform the partner.

In case of travel outside the European Union for dissemination, partners must send a request via email to the dissemination leader well in advance of the trip. The email must contain the following information:

- Who is travelling
- Destination of the trip
- Date of the trip
- The trip's relevance to the INNO4CFIs project.

The dissemination leader will examine the request and upon approval, it will forward the request with the recommended action to the PC. In the event the request is accepted the PC will forward the request to the Project Officer who has the final say on the matter. The partner will be informed of the decision.

6.3 Measuring project effort and costs

Following each internal quarterly management report, the PC will compare between actual efforts and costs against planned to measure variance. If the effort and cost has a variance of between 10% and 20% of planned the reporting partner must report the reason for the exception. If the variance is greater than 20% the reporting partner must report the reason for the exception and provide the EMU with a detailed corrective plan to bring the project's performance back to acceptable level.

Once the variation exceeds the 20% threshold the reporting partner must present the PC with options for corrective actions. The EMU will meet to select the best option. The partner will develop a corrective action plan to bring the project back on track. Once the EMU approves the plan, the change control procedure will be activated and the action plan will become part of the project plan.

6.4 Subcontracting

During the project, partners will be required to acquire from third parties the following services:

Work package n°	Partner responsible for subcontracting (acronym)	Task	Brief description of work
WP1	FEA	8.2	Call for action
WP2	NTUA	2.1	Self-assessment tool for SMEs
WP4	AINIA	4.1	Analysing the carbon footprint results
WP7	ABC	7.1	Business models design and implementation

WP9	CNR	9.1	Establishment of indicators and measuring tools
WP10	CIRCONNACT	10.1	Dissemination and communication activities

TABLE 10: SUBCONTRACTING OF SERVICES (TABLE AT PAGE 144 OF THE G.A.)

During the project, partners will be required to acquire equipment:

Beneficiary	Type	Total amount
PLANET	Improvement and maintenance of the MTP facility at Tinos Island living lab. Various tools (including mould and growth media) to manufacture and assemble the planting units. Various tools to assemble, maintain and repair the desalination units.	6.665,00
CNR	One thermostatic cabinet for growth of fungi. Leaf chlorophyll and flavonoid analyser. Precision laboratory scale.	44.000,00
	One Autoclave to sterilise substrates and materials. A vertical flow microbiological hood.	
	Portable and in situ small instruments for field measurements in plants (e.g. soil moisture sensors, plant water status, leaf area index, light sensor).	
	Two raw field laptops for download, control, registration and field data analysis during the field campaigns.	
	Instruments and devices for fungi cultivation will be used for bio incubator development.	
NTUA	Small tractor (or similar).	30.600,00
	Renting 1.5 hectare of land to plant the trees.	
NOVOBIOM	Validation site costs.	50.000,00
TreeO	Processing and analysis ground collected and remote sensing data.	2.100,00
RANCHO	Electronic devices in order to control and monitor energy, water and their environmental impact as well as CO2 emissions.	34.285,71
Space4Good	The budget is for acquiring commercial lidar, multispectral and/or optical data, for which the requirements will be	20,000.00

	defined through engagement with the consortium in WP4 and co-dependent WPs.	
--	---	--

Table 11: Equipment Acquisition

The PC has oversight of the procurement for the project through the Annual Financial Reports. The actual management for procurement activities falls with the budget holding partner. The partner is responsible for collecting bids, evaluating them, contracting the vendor and contract management. The partners are required to strictly adhere to the Annex I of Consortium Agreement guidelines for purchases. For deviations in purchases partners must obtain approval before proceeding with procurement according to section 6.2.

7. Schedule management plan

The project schedule is the roadmap for how the project will be executed. Schedules are an important part of any project as they provide the consortium with a clear picture of the project's status at any given time. The purpose of the schedule management plan is to define the approach to project schedule management including monitoring and controlling changes to the baseline. This includes identifying, analysing, documenting, prioritising, approving or rejecting, and publishing all schedule-related changes.

The project schedule will be reviewed by the PC and individual partners on a continuous three-month basis until the project end. In case of deviations, project partners must agree to the proposed resources, effort assignments, durations, schedule, and once this is achieved the PC will review and approve the schedule which will become the new baseline.

The Project Coordinator with the support of the SC will be responsible for facilitating the schedule development and adjustments. The PC will also create the project schedule using MS-Excel and validate the schedule with the SC and partners.

Figure 3, 4 and 5 illustrate the work plan for each year of the project's funding period:

FIGURE 3: WORKPLAN YEAR 1

FIGURE 4: WORKPLAN YEAR 2

FIGURE 5: WORKPLAN YEAR 3

The partners are responsible for participating in activity definition, sequencing, and duration and resource estimating. Partners will also review and validate the proposed schedule and perform assigned activities once the schedule is approved. The European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA) will participate in reviews of the proposed schedule through the annual project review and contract amendments as necessary.

7.1 Schedule control

The project schedule will be reviewed as necessary on a monthly basis by the respective WPLs, following recommendations received by the PC and/or SC. If a variance of 2 months or more is observed against the Schedule baseline at WP level, the respective WPL will inform the PC who in turn will review the project schedule. Otherwise, project schedule reviews will be held regularly by the PC and partners on a quarterly basis through the preparation of the internal quarterly work package progress report.

The partners are responsible for participating in schedule variance resolution activities as needed. The PC will communicate to the European Commission of the project schedule status and review/approve any schedule change requests as necessary.

8. Evaluation system

The quality control strategy of INNO4CFIs will ensure that quality is planned for both the deliverables and activities. This QAP will consist of the methodology on implementation of the project's internal guidelines for reporting and reviewing procedures to ensure the project's Quality Assurance. It will focus on the assessment of quality assurance, as well as monitoring and evaluation of project management, communication, dissemination strategies, working meetings and the steering group performance. It will review the quality of project outputs in the framework of quality indicators approved by all the partners. The monitoring of project progress and quality of outputs in each WP will ensure the high quality of project outcomes and will guarantee the compliance of project results with project objectives.

The evaluation system will be based on the following criteria:

1. Efficiency: how well are resources being used? The extent to which the intervention delivers, or is likely to deliver, results in an economic and timely way, as well as the coherence of the consumption of resources with the achieved outcomes and outputs, is evaluated through the analysis of the documents and of the interviews' outcomes.
2. Effectiveness: is the intervention achieving its objectives? The information collected through the analysis of the documentation and the interviews are analysed in order to assess the level of attainment of the objectives and results, using the indicators specified in the monitoring plan (section 2.2). It is important to evaluate:
 - a. Whether the indicators are still meaningful considering the possible evolution of the scenario;
 - b. Whether the quantitative targets set are still realistic;
 - c. The progress made, and whether it is in line with the expectations.
3. Impact: what difference does the intervention make? Following the interim reports an evaluation can be made of the extent to which the project has already produced a level of change for instance among the target groups (e.g. following WP2 analysis, considering the one participating in the project, etc.). This aspect will therefore be evaluated on the basis of the indicators set up in the project as well as in the quality and monitoring plan, on the analysis of the documents produced and according to the communication and dissemination plan activities and results (e.g. #of views, posts, etc.) and, finally as part of the interviews carried out with the partners.
4. Sustainability: will the benefits last? The sustainability of a project by definition can only be verified after the end of the funding phase, however at each interim report a number of aspects can be evaluated. For instance, considering questionnaires and feedback from the partners (e.g. will of the partners to implement the sustainability measures envisaged in the proposal, the commitment to introduce and pursue an innovation in the market, etc.).
5. Relevance: is the intervention doing the right things? To evaluate the relevance of a proposal it is important to know its context, markets and related evolutions. As such, it is important to verify that the objectives and expected results of the project are still in line with the identified needs. This can only be done through interactive sessions with partners, following the results of the activities and the deployment of the business model.

FIGURE 6: THE FOUR SOURCES OF INNO4CFIS ASSESSMENT

8.1 Consortium Assessment

According to the INNO4CFIs Project Management Strategy, while the WP Leaders are in charge of overseeing quality control, timely report delivery, and proper activity execution, each partner is accountable for the calibre of their individual activities. Throughout the project, there will be multiple interim evaluation sessions as well as a final evaluation conducted internally. The primary methods of evaluation will be interviews, questionnaires, and verbal feedback among the project partners and, when appropriate, among other stakeholders, such as SMEs, policy makers, investors and, universities. All the stakeholders have been properly identified via the Dissemination and Communication Plan (D10.1). Management meetings will be used also to discuss QA implementation. Internally the QAPT will implement various types of monitoring and quality control processes, such as questionnaires, peer reviews, evaluation surveys, internal institutional evaluation boards, timely work and performance indicators:

- Feedback from EU partners;
- timely work on the organisation and execution of planned activities;
- outreach projects performed regularly.

Moreover, the project consortium itself will also be asked about their ideas on where they see improvement potential, in particular for topics such as internal procedures and project outcomes. The survey will involve the main entities of the overall management structure, namely the Project coordinator, the Project manager, the Steering Committee and the Technical Committee. The evaluation takes place every 12 months, starting from September 2023. As Table 11 shows, four topics are evaluated within this survey; external communication, external collaboration, INNO4CFIs strategies and internal communication.

External communication
How do you assess the marketing of INNO4CFIs?
Which further promotion activities do you suggest?
External collaboration
How do you assess the collaboration with other EU initiatives?
How could the collaboration with other EU initiatives be improved?
Internal communication
How do you assess the communication within the team?
How could the communication within the team be improved?
INNO4CFIs strategies
How do you assess the quality of the execution of the strategies?
Which further activities could be implemented?

Table 12: survey topics

8.2 KPIs and Impact Assessment

The second key objective of the INNO4CFIs project assessment is the constant measuring, interpreting and displaying of relevant Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

In order to ensure the transparent display of the KPIs to the consortium, internal evaluation reports, based on the procedure and templates, shown in this paper, are contrived on a regular basis.

Table 12 shows the indicators that will be monitored and reported during the execution of the project.

<u>Outputs and results indicators</u>		
Specific Objective	Relevant KPI	Means of verification
S.O.1 - Implementing the stakeholder analysis according to the SME and Star-up needs of the identified regions using the WEFE Nexus methodology	Minimum 10 NEXUS cases mapped during the needs analysis phase	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Guided interviews ● Questionnaires ● KPIs inventory ● Number of NEXUS cases mapped ● Inventory of success cases and go-to- business scenario
	Identification of at least 3 customers and users to be involved in the validation phase	
	Definition of the KPIs inventory to measure carbon footprint in the WEFE Nexus real case scenario	

	Assessment tool for SMEs to measure carbon farming according to the WEFE Nexus methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Report on needs of low and moderate innovative regions ● INNO4CFIs: self-assessment tool for SMEs
S.O.2 - Demonstrating and validating the achievement of TRL8 for the Carbon Farm Technology Platform	Carbon Farm Technology Platform developed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Tech Carbon Footprint Report and KPIs ● Life Cycle Assessment report
	Technology model validated	
S.O.3 - Design and implementation of a low-power P2P platform equipped with Self-Sovereign Digital Id (SSID) and Smart contracts for the secure execution and management of Carbon Credit transactions	Biodiversity Carbon Credit System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Biodiversity Carbon Credit report ● End users questionnaires
S.O.4 - Validation of INNO4CFIs business model	8 trainings held with local partners before starting the pilot phase (2 each living hubs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Number of local operators trained to participate ● Number of local partners involved in the trainings ● Agroforestry project design ● Stakeholders guidelines: design establishment and evaluation of the INNO4CFIs Carbon Credit Model
	80 local operators of local partners trained on the project before the implementation of the pilot phase (10 each living hubs)	
	At least 6000 trees and biological species will be planted via the project alone (min. 1500 trees and biological species living hubs)	
	INNO4CFIs validated in 4 different living hubs Grosseto (Tuscany, IT), Thynos (Northern Cyclades, GR), Zamora (Castile and León, SP), Ottignies (Wallonia, BE)	

S.O.5 - Promote access to cascade funding for the implementation of highly innovative carbon farming technologies in the territories selected by the project, thus increasing their competitive advantage	1 guideline for the call for proposals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Number of applications in the cascade funding ● Number of industry and investor participants in the events ● % of satisfaction in the calls for proposal ● Open calls report ● Analytics on the submitted proposals and selected projects
	At least 8 experts selected for the Pitch Evaluation Board	
	At least 40 projects funded through 2 calls for proposals	
S.O.6 – Evaluate the sustainability of the INNO4CFIs business model	at least 5 MoU and/or cooperation agreements signed with similar business initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Number of agreements signed with business initiatives ● Number of supporters from private companies ● Number of supporters from investors and clusters
	INNO4CFIs business model (including the exploitation strategy)	
	INNO4CFIs exploitation and IPRs roadmap	

TABLE 13: KPI AND MONITORED INDICATORS THROUGHOUT THE PROJECT

8.3 Stakeholder assessment

Key stakeholders will be asked to assess the overall impact of INNO4CFIs, every 12 months starting from M12. The stakeholders answer questions on topics in the light of their own relation to the INNO4CFIs project, external dissemination & communication, collaboration experiences and objectives and impact. In order to evaluate the impact of the project, the last section (on objectives and impact) is intended to answer questions about target achievement and sustainability.

The objectives of INNO4CFIs, according to the I3-2021-INV1 call, are:

- Implementing the stakeholder analysis according to the SME and Start-up needs of the identified regions using the WEFE Nexus methodology.
- Demonstrating and validating the achievement of TRL8 for the Carbon Farm Technology Platform.
- Design and implementation of a low-power P2P platform equipped with Self-Sovereign Digital Id (SSID) and Smart contracts for the secure execution and management of Carbon Credit transactions.
- Validating the INNO4CFIs business model.

- Promote access to cascade funding for the implementation of highly innovative carbon farming technologies in the territories selected by the project, thus increasing their competitive advantage.
- Evaluate the sustainability of the INNO4CFIs business model.

General
Please describe your function in relation to the INNO4CFIs project project
How do you assess the general approach of INNO4CFIs?
How could the approach be improved?
Which possibilities do you see to continue the INNO4CFIs model after the end of the funding period?
External Communication & Dissemination
How do you assess the promotion related to the technologies implemented via the project?
External collaboration
How do you assess the collaboration with other European initiatives?
How do you assessthe communication with other stakeholders active in the European carbon farming sector?
Objectives & Impacts
How do you assess the achievements related to the main outcomes of the project, in particular the INNO4CFIs carbon farming platform and the blockchain smart contract system?

Table 14. STAKEHOLDERS ASSESSMENT

8.4 Cascade funding assessment

The project provides access to cascade funding for the implementation of highly innovative carbon farming technologies. In this regard, 1 or 2 calls for proposals are envisaged to SMEs and start-ups, which are active in the field of Carbon Farming in order to increase their competitive advantage. In order to assess the level of satisfaction and engagement of the participants in the cascade funding, they will be asked to fill out a questionnaire. Split selected participants and applicants.

Getting to know INNO4CFIs
How did you hear about the INNO4CFIs project and the cascade funding opportunity?
How useful do you assess the information provided? (via website, email, meetings)
Applying

What was your main reason to participate in the cascade funding?
How much effort did you spend to complete the application?
The application process was suitable and not too complex (degree of agreement from 1 to 10)
Did you receive correct information concerning timing, application, selection process etc?
Did you receive any extra assistance to understand the scope of the call? If yes, are you satisfied with it?
The experience
Did the contractual phase comply with your expectations?
Did the consortium support you during the implementation of the FSTP?
Did the consortium assign you a P.O?
Was the implementation of the FSTP activities aligned with the GA? How? If no, why?
Follow-up
Are you in touch with the members of the consortium? How?
Overall
How do you consider your experience?
Is there something that could be improved among the experience?
I have improved my know-how and technology (level of agreement 1-10)

Table 15. CASCADE FUNDING ASSESSMENT

ANNEXES

Annex I - Deliverable Template

Annex II - INNO4CFIs SlideMaster

Annex III - Deliverables Quality Assurance Check

Annex IV - Participant Feedback Form

Annex V - Event Report Templates (including participant feedback)

Annex VI - Risk Monitoring Sheet

ANNEX I

DELIVERABLE TEMPLATE

INNO4CFIs

Regenerative Carbon Farming

Title
Subtitle

Date

DELIVERABLE XX.Y	TITLE
Related Work Package	Stet clita kasd gubergren
Deliverable lead	Lorem ipsum dolor
Author(s)	Stet clita kasd gubergren Stet clita kasd gubergren Stet clita kasd gubergren
Contact	lorem@ipsum.com
Reviewer	Stet clita kasd
Grant Agreement Number	101115156
Funding body	Dolore magna aliquyam
Start date	01. Sept 2023
Project Duration	36 months
Type of Delivery (R, DEM, DEC, Other)¹	R = Report
Dissemination Level (PU, CO, CI)²	PU = Public
Date Last update	15.11.2023
Approved by	Eleonora Lombardi, Fondazione E. Amaldi
Website	www.inno4cfis.eu

DISCLAIMER

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Table of Content

- Table of Content 2**
- Heading Style..... 3**
- Heading 1 3**
 - Heading 2..... 3
 - Heading 3..... 3
- Lists 4**
 - Ordered List..... 4
 - Unordered List..... 4
- Other Formats 5**
 - Quote Style 1 5
 - Quote Style 2 5
- Table Styles 6**
 - Table Style 1..... 6
 - Table Style 2..... 7
 - Table Style 3..... 7

Heading Style

Heading 1

Heading 2

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Heading 6

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Lists

Ordered List

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2. Stet clita kasd gubergren, no sea takimata sanctus est Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur sadipscing elitr:

Unordered List

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Other Formats

Quote Style 1

“At vero eos et accusam et justo duo dolores et ea rebum. Stet clita kasd gubergren, no sea takimata sanctus est. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet. Et justo duo dolores et ea rebum. Sea takimata sanctus.”

Quote Style 2

“At vero eos et accusam et justo duo dolores et ea rebum. Stet clita kasd gubergren, no sea takimata sanctus est. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet. Et justo duo dolores et ea rebum. Sea takimata sanctus.”

Table Styles

Table Style 1

DELIVERABLE 10.1	COMMUNICATION STRATEGY
Related Work Package	Stet clita kasd gubergren
Deliverable lead	Lorem ipsum dolor
Author(s)	Stet clita kasd gubergren Stet clita kasd gubergren Stet clita kasd gubergren
Contact	lorem@ipsum.com
Reviewer	Stet clita kasd
Grant Agreement Number	0123456
Funding body	Dolore magna aliquyam
Start date	01. Nov 2023
Project Duration	24 months
Type of Delivery (R, DEM, DEC, Other)¹	R = Report
Dissemination Level (PU, CO, CI)²	PU = Public
Date Last update	15.03.2024
Approved by	Lorem Ipsum
Website	www.inno4cfis.eu

Table Style 2

DELIVERABLE 10.1	COMMUNICATION STRATEGY
Related Work Package	Stet clita kasd gubergren
Deliverable lead	Lorem ipsum dolor
Author(s)	Stet clita kasd gubergren Stet clita kasd gubergren Stet clita kasd gubergren
Contact	lorem@ipsum.com
Reviewer	Stet clita kasd
Grant Agreement Number	0123456
Funding body	Dolore magna aliquyam
Start date	01. Nov 2023
Project Duration	24 months
Type of Delivery (R, DEM, DEC, Other)¹	R = Report
Dissemination Level (PU, CO, CI)²	PU = Public
Date Last update	15.03.2024
Approved by	Lorem Ipsum
Website	www.inno4cfis.eu

Table Style 3

D 10.1	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur	M1 - M3	Jan 2024
D 10.2	Nonumy eirmod tempor	M4	Feb 2024
D 10.3	At vero et accusam	M7	Mar 2024

ANNEX II
INNOFCFIs SlideMaster

ANNEX III
Deliverable Quality Assurance Check

Annex C: Quality Assurance Checklist for Review of Deliverable

Autor(s) Responsible for the deliverable:

WP Leader:

Reviewers:

Indicator(s)	Scope of the Review	Assessment	Comments	Recommendations
Compliance with the objectives of the project	Does the deliverable comply with the objectives of the project?	Yes No Partially		
Compliance with the S.O. of the WP	Does the deliverable comply with the S.O. of the related WP?	Yes No Partially		
Correspondence with the description of work within the task	Does the deliverable correspond with the activity description as specified in the G.A.?	Yes No Partially		
Compliance with the deliverable format	Is the use of the deliverable template (Annex A) correct?	Yes No Partially		
Adequacy of complementary information	Examples of complementary info: external sources used, library, list of contacts, methodology used.	Yes No Partially		
Overall assessment and suggestion for improvements				

ANNEX IV
Participant Feedback Form

Dear Participant,

Thank you for attending this event. In our effort to improve the organisation and the impact of these events we invite you to complete the following questionnaire. In most of the questions you will be asked to rate your satisfaction on a scale by ticking the appropriate answer. In some of the questions you will be asked to describe your personal opinion in a few words and to give suggestions for future improvements of the content and overall organisation of the event.

We appreciate your valuable contribution and we thank you in advance!

General information

Sex (Please mark the appropriate answer):

Female ; Male ; Nonbinary Defined ; Prefer not to declare

Country

What is your present professional position?

Overall Feedback

Overall, how satisfied were you with:

	Most satisfied	Satisfied	Moderately satisfied	Rather dissatisfied	Not at all satisfied
The event administration	5	4	3	2	1
The structure of the programme	5	4	3	2	1
The venue and facilities	5	4	3	2	1
The presentations	5	4	3	2	1
The discussions	5	4	3	2	1

Please indicate your agreement with the following statements by ticking the appropriate number:

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
The information I got will be of immediate use to me.	5	4	3	2	1
This event covered to a very high extent the topics I have expected.	5	4	3	2	1
I enjoyed the cooperation and interaction with the other participants	5	4	3	2	1
My expectations about this event were met or exceeded	5	4	3	2	1
The materials distributed are useful and informative	5	4	3	2	1

The discussions were relevant for the participants	5	4	3	2	1
The methods of working were suitable for the topics and for the participants.	5	4	3	2	1
The overall organisation was professional	5	4	3	2	1
The time management was always to my fullest satisfaction.	5	4	3	2	1
The style and level of communication between organisers and participants was professional.	5	4	3	2	1
I would recommend this kind of event to my colleagues.	5	4	3	2	1

Strengths and improvements

- a) Have you participated in similar events before? Yes " No
- b) Please illustrate any strengths of the event and contributions or activities you enjoyed:
- c) Please indicate how you think the event could have been improved:
- d) Any further comments?

ANNEX V
Event Report Template

EVENT REPORT TEMPLATE (Annex V of Quality Control and Monitoring Plan)

This template has to be filled by project partners (organisers) for all INNO4CFIs events (except SC/consortium meetings). Furthermore, this template can be used to inform colleagues and partners about other events attended (promoting INNO4CFIs). In the second case please just fill in the first page and delete the chapters thereafter.

Author:	
Event Title:	
Event Date:	
Event Venue:	
Type of event: (National, international, press conference, promotional event etc.)	
Short description:	
Organiser(s):	
Agenda:	Link to the agenda
Total number of participants:	
Links to further information:	
Other personal remarks:	
<p>Here you can include the information such: Presentation of INNO4CFIs at the event? What was the subject of your presentation? Were you invited to present INNO4CFIs or you have registered for the event for other reasons? Were INNO4CFIs promotional materials presented at the event? Which type? (e.g. Leaflet, roll up, stand, etc.)</p>	

EVENT ORGANISATION DETAILS

Invitation was sent off to participants on:	
Information Material was sent off to participants on:	
Date of Initial Participant List Compilation:	
Date of Final Participant List Compilation:	
Total Number of Participants Invited	
Date of Agenda Finalisation:	
???	
???	

Problems encountered during the event preparation phase (To be filled by organisers)

EVENT ROLLOUT

Some general information (to be filled by organisers)

Final Event Agenda + Participant list

Please attach the final event agenda and the list of participants

Event Implementation – Commentary by Organising Partners

ANNEX VI
Risk Monitoring Sheet

RISK MONITORING SHEET (Annex VI of Quality Control and Monitoring Plan)

The Risk Monitoring Sheet in INNO4CFIs should be updated after each Steering Committee Meeting (risk brainstorming). The scope of this template is to guide the partners towards the updating of the risks and their mitigation measures according to the project implementation.

Risk Title:

Description of the risk	Probably : Low, medium, high Impact : Low, medium, high	Remarks if needed
Mitigation measures (planned)		
Actual measures (taken)		
Decision (if applicable)	To be filled in only if a decision has been taken over the risks (e.g. the risk occurred and led to a change in the G.A. or C.A., etc.)	